

Solvent-free microwave-expedited synthesis of ferrocenylenones and ferrocenyl-1,5-diketones using hydrotalcite

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Abstract : An efficient, facile microwave-assisted synthesis of ferrocenylenones and ferrocenyl-1,5-diketones is described using hydrotalcite as base under solvent-free condition. This protocol is extremely fast and is applicable to a wide variety of substrates.

Keywords : Acetophenone, acetylferrocene, aromatic aldehydes, ferrocenylchalcones, ferrocenylenones, 1,5-diketones, hydrotalcite.

Introduction

Since the first discovery of a hyperpolarizable ferrocene derivative displaying a large second-order optical non-linearity¹, a range of suitably functionalised crystalline², polymeric³ and amphiphilic⁴ ferrocene derivatives displaying a high degree of non-linear optical (NLO) behaviour have been reported. Ferrocene derivatives as new NLO materials remain at the forefront of attention offering advantage over other organometallics due to their synthetic versatility and overall thermal and photochemical stability⁵. Aldol reactions are one of the reactions extensively used for the synthesis of various ferrocene derivatives exhibiting NLO behaviour⁶. The aldol reactions are usually carried out under classical homogeneous conditions in ethanol⁷⁻¹⁰. In most cases, the condensation of ferrocenyl derivatives has been focused on the Claisen-Schmidt reaction of ferrocenecarbaldehyde with aromatic aldehyde or ketone in homogenous solutions¹¹. However, the method suffers from serious disadvantages, such as low product yields^{12,13} and the use of large amount of solvents¹⁴.

1,5-Diketones are significant synthetic intermediates and efficient starting materials for the synthesis of various heterocyclic and polyfunctional compounds¹⁵⁻¹⁷. Ferrocene substituted 1,5-diketones are known to have potential applications^{18,19} in the field of chemistry. 1,5-

Diketones can be synthesized by (a) the aldol Michael addition strategy; (b) the addition of active methylene compounds to α,β -unsaturated ketones²⁰; (c) the conjugate addition of enones to trimethylsilylenol ethers as donor²¹ and (d) the condensation of ketone enolate and Mannich base derived from methyl ketones²². Among all methods, the method (c) is considered to be the best one but it should be conducted in a moisture-free and oxygen-free condition. Other methods have typical disadvantages such as use of alkaline alcohols under refluxing conditions, longer synthetic routes, longer reaction time, self-condensation, cyclisation, retro-Michael reaction. A solid state Michael addition has also been reported²³⁻²⁵.

Recently, some aldol reactions are described, using microwave radiation and 18-crown-6 as catalyst, with pulverized KOH or NaOH in the absence of a solvent^{26,27} and a solvent-free approach using NaOH as base has been reported for the synthesis of ferrocenyl-1,5-diketones²⁸. Though these methods are economical and simple, yet the use of strong base such as NaOH is undesirable as they result in the production of large amount of industrial waste.

With the increased environmental awareness, close attention has been paid to the development of environmental friendly protocols. Hence, there has been a gradual change from traditional reaction conditions to more eco-

friendly routes. This growth of green chemistry holds significant potential for the reduction of the by-products, a reduction in waste production and lowering of energy costs.

The applications of microwave energy in chemical reactions are increasing very rapidly²⁹ since the pioneering reports of Giguere³⁰ and Gedye³¹. The time saving ability together with the very short response times and the minimization of thermal decomposition products, fewer side reactions³² higher yield of products are the main advantages of microwave heating. Hydrotalcite or anionic clays are homogeneous mixed hydroxides with a brucite-like layer structure. They have shown to be highly active catalyst for the epoxidation of olefins using H₂O₂ in the presence of nitrile³³⁻³⁵.

As part of the ongoing program on environmentally benign chemical synthesis employing alternative reaction conditions and media, herein we report an expeditious and environmentally benign protocol for the synthesis of various ferrocenylenones using hydrotalcite as base for

the first time with/without solvent, in the presence/absence of phase-transfer catalyst, Aliquat-336^{36,37} at room temperature or microwave irradiation³⁸ condition and also herewith we report the synthesis of ferrocenyl-1,5-diketones using hydrotalcite as base under solvent-free/microwave irradiation condition.

Results and discussion

The results of the synthesis of various ferrocenylenones **3(a-j)** and **6(a-e)** were summarized in Tables 1 and 2 respectively. The reactions of acetylferrocene **1** with various aromatic aldehydes **2(a-j)** in ethanol at room temperature in the absence of Aliquat-336, was found to be incomplete even after 24 h. Typically, the reaction of acetylferrocene **1** with *p*-methoxybenzaldehyde **2b** was sluggish at room temperature in ethanol. But in the presence of Aliquat-336 under solvent-free condition, at room temperature 60% of **3b** was obtained in 35 min. However, 75% of **3b** was obtained in 6 min with Aliquat-336 under solvent-free microwave irradiation condition. The condensation of ferrocenecarbaldehyde **4** with ketone **5(a-**

Table 1. Synthesis of ferrocenylenones **3(a-j)**

Entry	Ar	Method A		Method B		Method C		M.p. (°C)
		Time (min)	Yield (%)	Time (min)	Yield (%)	Time (min)	Yield (%)	
a		24	43	30	70	5.0	83	140-141
b		24	38	36	60	8.0	75	149-150
c		16	46	20	75	4.0	90	224-225
d		15	48	20	80	3.0	90	191-192
e		18	42	30	77	4.0	85	195-196
f		22	40	30	75	4.5	83	173-174
g		20	40	30	73	4.5	80	151-152
h		18	46	20	74	4.0	86	158-160
i		22	43	30	76	4.0	83	207-208
j		20	45	25	74	5.0	83	148-149

Table 2. Synthesis of ferrocenylenones 6(a-e)

Entry	Ar	Method A		Method B		Method C		M.p. (°C)
		Time (h)	Yield (%)	Time (min)	Yield (%)	Time (min)	Yield (%)	
a		18	43	30	74	5.0	90	141-142
b		16	48	25	81	3.4	94	150-151
c		15	46	30	76	4.1	90	186-187
d		16	42	30	78	4.2	86	137-138
e		15	45	30	72	3.3	92	157-158

Method A : Ethanol, room temperature.

Method B : Hydrotalcites, Aliquat-336, room temperature.

Method C : Hydrotalcites, Aliquat-336, microwave irradiation.

e) afforded the ferrocenylenones 6(a-e) in highest yield in a short duration of time, in the presence of Aliquat-336 under solvent-free microwave irradiation condition.

Table 3. Michael addition of acetophenone 8 on ferrocenylenones 7(a-g) : Synthesis of ferrocenyl-1,5-diketones 9(a-g) using hydrotalcite

Pdt.	R	Method				M.p. (°C)/lit. ¹²
		A		B		
		T ^h	Y	T ^m	Y	
9a	Ph	1.0	80	10	93	108/105
9b	4-Cl-C ₆ H ₄	1.0	89	12	95	140/137
9c	4-Me ₂ N-C ₆ H ₄	1.5	86	15	90	140/140
9d	3-O ₂ N-C ₆ H ₄	1.0	90	6.0	98	141/140
9e	2-Furyl	1.1	85	10	91	93/93
9f	Ph-CH=CH-	1.1	83	9.0	90	130/129
9g	Fc	1.0	89	10	96	120/119

T^h = Time in hours; T^m = Time in minutes; Y = Yield in %.

Method A : Hydrotalcite/50 °C/solvent-free condition.

Method B : Hydrotalcite/solvent-free condition/microwave irradiation.

A series of ferrocenyl-1,5-diketones 9(a-g) are prepared through Michael addition between ferrocenyl chalcone 7(a-g) and acetophenone 8 using hydrotalcite as base under; (a) solvent-free condition, (b) solvent-free/microwave irradiation (Scheme 3). The results of microwave-assisted solvent-free synthesis of ferrocenyl-1,5-diketones over hydrotalcite are summarized in Table 3 along with comparative reaction, under solvent-free condition without microwave irradiation. Recently, the synthesis of 1,5-dioxo-3,5-diphenyl ferrocene was accomplished by

conjugate addition of enones by enolates derived from base-induced cleavage of the O-Si bond of the trimethylsilylenoether under argon atmosphere²¹. The operation is tedious as well as expensive. Another method²⁸, involves the use of five fold amount of acetophenone **8** (Michael donor) and one fold amount of ferrocenyl chalcone **7a** using strong base NaOH under solvent-free condition, for the synthesis of 1,5-dioxo-3,5-diphenylpentyl ferrocene **9a**. Excess acetophenone in the presence of such a strong base NaOH can undergo self-condensation apart from affording ferrocenyl-1,5-diketone **9a**. We found that compound **9a** could be effectively synthesized in 80% yield by taking one fold amount of ferrocenyl chalcone **7a** and 1.5 fold amount of acetophenone **2** under solvent-free/microwave condition over hydrotalcite. The rate of the reaction is also found to be substituent dependent. The presence of an electron-withdrawing group in the ferrocenyl chalcone **7(a-g)** facilitates Michael-addition than electron-donating group in the ferrocenyl chalcone **7(a-g)**, but the yield of the ferrocenyl-1,5-diketones are found to be excellent using hydrotalcite, irrespective of the nature of the substituent present in the phenyl group. We also observed that 1,4-addition prevails over 1,6-addition as in the case of the ferrocenyl chalcone **7f**, as Michael acceptor and acetophenone **8** as Michael-donor over hydrotalcite at 50 °C under solvent-free condition, affording an excellent yield of 85% **9f** in 1.1 h. Faster rate of reaction and product yield (**9f**; 90%) in 9 min is observed, when the reaction is subjected to microwave irradiation under solvent-free condition.

All the ferrocenylenones **3(a-j)** and **6(a-e)** and the ferrocenyl-1,5-diketones **9(a-g)** synthesized using hydrotalcite as base gave satisfactory IR, ¹H NMR, ¹³C NMR and elemental analysis. Melting points of the products **3(a-j)**, **6(a-e)** and **3(a-g)** were compared with the literature reports and found to be satisfactory.

Experimental

General procedure for the condensation of acetylferrocene 1 with aromatic aldehydes 2(a-j) using hydrotalcite : Synthesis of ferrocenylenones 3(a-j) :

Method A : Acetylferrocene **1** (1 mmol), aldehyde **2** (1.1 mmol), hydrotalcite (1 mmol) in ethanol (25 ml) was stirred at room temperature for the specified time (Table 1). The solvent was removed under reduced pressure. The crude product was extracted with dichloromethane

(2 × 25 ml). After filtration on celite, the solvent was removed and the residue was chromatographed on alumina (Brockmann activity III) using hexane eluent.

Method B : To a mixture of acetylferrocene **1** (1 mmol), aldehyde **2** (1.1 mmol), hydrotalcite (1 mmol), a drop of Aliquat-336 was added and the mixture was stirred for the specified time (Table 1). The solid obtained was extracted with dichloromethane (2 × 25 ml). After filtration on celite, the solvent was removed and the residue was chromatographed on alumina (Brockmann activity III) using hexane as eluent.

Method C : A mixture of acetylferrocene **1** (1 mmol), aldehyde **2** (1.1 mmol), hydrotalcite (1 mmol), Aliquat-336 (1 drop) was subjected to microwave irradiation (140 W, 2450 MHz) for the specified time (Table 1). The solid obtained was cooled at room temperature and extracted with dichloromethane (2 × 25 ml). After filtration on celite, the solvent was removed and the residue was chromatographed on alumina (Brockmann activity III) using hexane as eluent.

General procedure for the condensation of ferrocenecarbaldehyde 4 with various ketones 5(a-e) using hydrotalcites : Synthesis of ferrocenylenones 6(a-e) :

Method A : A mixture of ferrocenecarbaldehyde **4** (1 mmol), ketone **5** (1.1 mmol), hydrotalcite (1 mmol) in ethanol (25 ml) was stirred at room temperature for the specified time (Table 2). The solvent was removed under reduced pressure. The crude product was extracted with dichloromethane (2 × 25 ml). After filtration on celite, the solvent was removed and the residue was chromatographed on alumina (Brockmann activity III) using hexane : ethyl acetate (9 : 1) as eluent.

Method B : To a mixture of ferrocenecarbaldehyde **4** (1 mmol), ketone **5** (1 mmol), hydrotalcite (1 mmol), a drop of Aliquat-336 was added and the mixture was stirred at room temperature for the specified time (Table 2). The crude product was extracted with dichloromethane (2 × 25 ml). After filtration on celite, the solvent was removed and the residue was chromatographed on alumina (Brockmann activity III) using hexane : ethyl acetate (9 : 1) as eluent.

Method C : A mixture of ferrocenecarbaldehyde **4** (1 mmol), ketone **5** (1 mmol), hydrotalcite (1 mmol), Aliquat-336 (1 drop), was subjected to microwave irradiation for the specified time (Table 2). The solid obtained was cooled at room temperature and then extracted with

dichloromethane (2 × 25 ml). After filtration on celite, the solvent was removed and the residue was chromatographed on alumina (Brockmann activity III) using hexane : ethyl acetate (9 : 1) as eluent.

General procedure for the synthesis of ferrocenyl-1,5-diketones 9(a-g) :

Method A : A mixture of ferrocenylchalcone **7** (1 mmol), acetophenone **8** (2 mmol) and hydrotalcite (0.25 g), was ground with an agate mortar and a pestle and allowed to stand at 50 °C for a specified time as shown in Table 3. The final products were extracted with dichloromethane (2 × 25 ml) and the solution was dried over anhydrous MgSO₄. After filtration on celite, the solvent was removed under reduced pressure and the crude product was subjected to column chromatography using alumina (Brockmann activity III) using petroleum-ethyl acetate (5%) as eluent.

Method B : A mixture of ferrocenylchalcone **7** (1 mmol), acetophenone **8** (2 mmol) and hydrotalcite (0.25 g), was ground with an agate mortar and a pestle, and the mixture was subjected to microwave irradiation (140 W, 2250 Hz) for the specified time as shown in Table 3. The solid mixture was then allowed to cool at room temperature. The solid mixture was extracted with dichloromethane (2 × 25 ml) and the solution was dried over anhydrous MgSO₄. After filtration on celite, the solvent was removed under reduced pressure and crude product was subjected to column chromatography using alumina (Brockmann activity III) using petroleum ether-ethyl acetate (5%) as eluent.

We have observed that in the synthesis of ferrocenylones **3(a-j)** and **6(a-e)** there is moderate to good yield if we adopt Method A and Method B and there is excellent yields if we adopt Method C and also in the synthesis of ferrocenyl-1,5-diketone **9(a-g)** there is a good yield if we adopt Method A and there is an excellent yield if we adopt Method B.

In conclusion, we report a first instance where hydrotalcite is used as base for the first time for an efficient solvent-free microwave-assisted synthesis of ferrocenylones and ferrocenyl-1,5-diketones under microwave irradiation. The rapid reaction rate and high yield of product is a consequence of selective absorption of microwave energy by the polar molecules during the course

of the reaction. This approach significantly minimizes the longer reaction time and avoids the use of large excess of organic solvent usually employed in conventional method.

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References

1. M. L. H. Green, S. R. Marder, M. E. Thompson, J. A. Bandy, D. Bloor, P. V. Kolinsky and R. J. Jones, *Nature*, 1987, **330**, 360.
2. J. W. Perry, A. E. Stiegman, S. E. Marder and D. R. Coulter, "In Organic Materials for Nonlinear Optics", eds. R. A. Hann and D. Bloor. The Royal Society of Chemistry, London, England, 1989, No. 69.
3. M. E. Wright, E. G. Topilkar, R. F. Kubin and M. D. Seltzer, *Macromolecules*, 1990, **25**, 1838.
4. G. G. Roberts, B. Holcroft, D. Richardson and R. Colbrook, *J. Chim. Phys.*, 1988, **85**, 1093.
5. E. W. Neuse, J. R. Woodhouse, G. Montaudo and C. Puglisi, *Appl. Organomet. Chem.*, 1988, **85**, 1093.
6. E. Stankovic, S. Toma, R. V. Boxel, I. Asselberghs and A. Persoons, *J. Organomet. Chem.*, 2001, **637**, 426.
7. K. Schlogl, *Monatsh. Chem.*, 1957, **88**, 601.
8. P. Furdick, P. Elecko, S. Toma and J. Suchy, *Chem. Zvesti.*, 1960, **15**, 501.
9. (a) J. Biochard, J. P. Morin and J. Tirouflet, *J. Bull. Soc. Chim. Fr.*, 1963, 851; (b) J. Tirouflet and J. Biochard, *Compt. Rend.*, 1960, **250**, 1861; (c) 1960, **251**, 1394.
10. M. Salisova, M. Puciova, V. N. Postnov and S. Toma, *Chem. Pap.*, 1990, **44**, 201.
11. M. Wolf-Drobmar, "Gmelin Handbook", In : 'Fe-Org. Comp. Part A. Freeocene 8', 8th ed., Springer-Verlag, Berlin, Heidelberg, New York, Tokyo, 1986, p. 38.
12. P. Elecko, *Chem. Zvesti.*, 1969, **23**, 168.
13. F. D. Popp and E. B. Moynahan, *J. Heterocycl. Chem.*, 1970, **7**, 351.
14. J. A. Winstead, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1972, **37**, 1271.
15. Z. S. Arigan and H. Suschitky, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1961, 2245.
16. S. S. Hirsch and W. J. Bailey, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1978, **43**, 4091.
17. F. Krohnke, *Synthesis*, 1976, 1.
18. T. K. Potts, *Bull. Soc. Chem. Belg.*, 1990, **99**, 741.
19. E. C. Constable and A. M. W. Cargill Thompson, *J.*

- Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 1992, 2947.
20. I. R. Butler and S. J. McDonald, *Polyhedron*, 1995, **14**, 529.
 21. V. M. Swamy and A. Sarka, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1998, **39**, 1261.
 22. N. S. Gill, K. B. James, F. Lions and K. T. Potts, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1952, **74**, 4923.
 23. B. S. Goud, K. Panneerselvam, D. E. Zacharias and J. Desiraju, *J. Chem. Soc., Perkin Trans.*, 1995, **2**, 325.
 24. S. Annunziata, S. Aldo, R. D. Margherita, G. Manueia and S. Arrigo, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1997, **38**, 289.
 25. X. L. Li, Y. M. Wang, T. Matsuura and J. B. Meng, *J. Heterocycl. Chem.*, 1999, **36**, 697.
 26. F. Toda, K. Tanaka and K. Hamai, *J. Chem. Soc., Perkin Trans. 1*, 1990, 3207.
 27. W. Liu, Q. Xu, B. Chen, Y. Liang and Y. Ma, *J. Organomet. Chem.*, 2001, **484**, 27.
 28. W. Y. Liu, Q. H. Xu, Y. M. Liang, B. H. Chen, W. M. Liu and Y. X. Ma, *J. Organomet. Chem.*, 2001, **637**, 719.
 29. D. M. P. Mingos and D. R. Baghurst, *Chem. Soc. Rev.*, 1991, **20**, 1.
 30. R. J. Giguere, T. L. Bray, S. M. Duncan and G. Majetich, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1986, **27**, 4945.
 31. R. Gedye, F. Smith, K. Westaway, H. Ali, L. Baldisera, L. Laberge and J. Roussel, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1986, **27**, 279.
 32. D. Villemin, B. Martin, M. Puciova and S. Toma, *J. Organomet. Chem.*, 1994, **484**, 27.
 33. F. Cavani, F. Trifiro and A. Vaccari, *Catal. Today*, 1991, **11**, 173.
 34. K. Yamaguchi, K. Mori, T. Mizugaki, K. Ebitani and K. Kaneda, *J. Org. Chem.*, 2000, **65**, 6897.
 35. (a) J. M. Fraile, J. I. Garcia, D. Marco and J. A. Mayoral, *Appl. Catal. (A) Gen.*, 2001, **207**, 239; (b) J. M. Fraile, J. I. Garcia and J. A. Mayoral, *Catal. Today*, 2000, **57**, 3; (c) J. M. Fraile, J. I. Garcia, J. A. Mayoral and F. Figueras, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1996, **37**, 5995.
 36. C. M. Stark, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1971, **93**, 195.
 37. A. Loupy, G. Bram and J. Sausoulet, *New. J. Chem.*, 1992, **16**, 233 and references cited.
 38. G. Bram, A. Loupy, D. Villemin and K. Smith (ed.), "In Solid Supports and Catalysis in Organic Synthesis", Ellis Horwood and Prentice Hall, 1992, Chap. 12, 302.